

Advanced Data Products for Radio Observatories

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Abstract

This white paper¹ discusses the importance of Advanced Data Products (ADPs) for radio observatories. It outlines the current state, key lessons learned, and future directions.

1 Introduction

Advanced Data Products (ADPs) are increasingly recognized as a key component for enhancing the scientific output and operational efficiency of radio observatories. In an era characterized by the exponential growth of data volumes, the complexity of scientific data analysis and an increased level of inter-connectivity within the scientific community that has driven new community-wide changes and research-based processes, ADPs provide a structured approach to further bridge the gap between raw observational data and scientific results, e.g. by reducing the time to answer specific science questions or providing products tuned to specific science use cases.

ADPs are vital not only for simplifying data analysis by significantly reducing the time, effort, and resources required, but also for democratizing access to high-quality data, enabling a broader scientific community to leverage these resources effectively. In turn, these products can enable a

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wide audience to exploit the data in creative ways beyond the goals of the original project that generated them. By offering ready-to-use data products, beyond the standard ones already generated by observatories, radio ADPs open up access to a wider range of researchers, including those from institutions with limited computational resources or non-radio expertise, to contribute to and benefit from scientific discoveries in the radio domain. Furthermore, ADPs facilitate cross-disciplinary research by standardizing data formats and integrating metadata that supports interoperability among different archives and platforms.

This paper summarizes the presentations and group discussions that occurred during the recent ADP2024 workshop, that took place at the European Southern Observatory (ESO) in Garching, on 10-12 December 2024 (link). It aims to provide an overview of the current state of radio ADPs amongst a representative set of major interferometric observatories, the lessons learned from their implementation, and strategic recommendations for their future development. By addressing the challenges and opportunities associated with ADPs, we seek to lay the groundwork for their broader adoption and optimization in the radio astronomy community.

2 Background

The concept of ADPs has evolved alongside advancements in observational capabilities and data processing technologies, as well as an increased level of inter-connectivity within the scientific community. Historically, the focus of radio observatories was limited to data collection, with minimal attention given to post-observation data processing. However, the growing recognition of the value of archival data has shifted this focus toward creating science-optimized or high-level science-ready² products that can be immediately used by researchers, including those without high level expertise in the telescope-specific data-reduction techniques.

Key milestones in the development of ADPs include establishing quality assurance standards, exploring best-practices integrating machine learning algorithms for efficient data processing, and creating user-friendly interfaces that facilitate data exploration and analysis. These efforts have laid the groundwork for a paradigm shift in data management, where the focus is on maximizing the scientific value of observational data.

3 What are ADPs and Why Are They Important?

ADPs encompass a wide range of data outputs, including datasets with advanced calibration, high-level science products (HLSPs), and derived data products tailored to specific scientific objectives. Unlike raw data, which requires extensive processing before it can be analyzed, ADPs are designed to be of immediate quantifiable value, significantly reducing the time and effort required for scientific research, or freeing expertise, time, and resources for higher level processing or more direct interpretation.

3.1 ADP Diversity and Harmonization

“Astronomers want more information, not more data.” (F. Stoehr)

The definition of ADPs differs across observatories, reflecting varying scientific priorities and capabilities. ADPs may also differ within an observatory. For instance, the products delivered by ALMA³ Large Programs vary from project to project based on their science goals. Given this large range, it is critical that ADPs be standardized as much as is feasible, so that scientists can use them efficiently and combine them with ADPs from other observatories. This approach greatly enhances consistency and reliability across datasets. This standardization is achieved through the implementation of stringent quality assurance protocols and the adoption of interoperable data formats. The general idea is that,

²A science-ready product is a dataset that has been largely freed of instrument signatures (e.g., through calibration), has undergone quality assurance, and is well-characterized, allowing scientists to perform scientific analysis directly with minimal need for specific expertise in the instrument or data reduction procedures. This definition serves as a practical guideline for the purposes of the present document and is not intended to impose a rigid or subjective distinction between datasets of varying processing levels.

³Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array

with ADPs, size and compute requirements decrease, from a user point of view, while direct science relevance may increase.

3.2 Benefits of ADPs

The advantages of ADPs are numerous, both practical and strategic.

- **Accelerated research:** By providing science-ready data, ADPs enable researchers to focus on analysis and discovery rather than data processing.
- **Enhanced accessibility and education:** ADPs lower barriers to data use by providing high-quality, science-ready products accessible to a broad audience, including early-career researchers and non-expert institutions. This accessibility empowers the next generation of astronomers to broaden their expertise beyond their initial focus areas, fostering versatility and deeper scientific knowledge.
- **Facilitated collaboration:** Standardized data formats and metadata support cross-disciplinary research and collaboration, fostering innovation and discovery. By adhering to common standards, these formats also enable the seamless integration of multiple specialized programs and analysis codes, allowing researchers to combine diverse tools and methodologies to address complex scientific problems more effectively.
- **Efficient data processing:** ADPs can streamline data workflows, reducing redundancy and optimizing the use of computational resources. This is particularly important given the orders of magnitude increase in the data and required processing for coming systems.
- **Increased scientific impact:** The availability of high-quality data products enhances the visibility and impact of observatory science, attracting a larger and more scientifically diverse user community. This in turn increases the science return and value of publicly-funded facilities.
- **Increased reproducibility:** The formalization of the generation of ADPs increases reproducibility.
- **Reducing environmental impact:** If an observatory can deliver a high-quality product of general use, then it avoids multiple science teams performing identical compute-intensive operations to create the same product separately.

Scientific applications that demonstrate the transformative potential of ADPs include the rapid identification of transient phenomena, the integration of multi-wavelength data for comprehensive analyses, and the development of machine learning models for automated data classification.

3.3 Example ADPs

The following are a few example ADPs. In general, some will be observatory-specific, while others will be science-specific, such that the present list is far from complete.

- **Advanced calibration:** a standard observatory calibration process may not be optimum for specific scientific investigations. For instance, continuum images from radio observatories across the frequency spectrum are often dynamic range limited rather than thermal noise limited. As such, self-calibration techniques and direction-dependent calibration techniques are necessary to reach the desired imaging dynamic range. Furthermore, Solar System objects often need self-calibration using a priori models for their structure to reach their maximum possible dynamic range. In those cases, a different/advanced set of calibrated visibilities would be critical.
- **Combined imaging (across projects and/or observatories):** observatories will typically generate images from combining data from, at most, the same PI project. However, given that some targets can often be observed again across observing cycles, there might be great scientific potential in making images from data collected across not only PI projects, but also observatories.

One clear example of such interest is the ALMACAL project⁴, which obtained deep-field images by combining data from ALMA phase calibrator scans across multiple PI projects.

- **Additional imaging products:** in the case ALMA, the Pipeline produces IQUV images for polarization projects. These images could easily be converted into polarization fraction and position angle maps as ADPs.
- **Derived products:** These are commonly referred to as “high-level science products” — data products obtained through additional processing of the standard outputs generated by an observatory pipeline. Such products may be derived from imaging data or calibration data, for example through techniques such as UV modeling.
- **Enhanced search:** To support users who wish to download images or raw data for generating their own ADPs, advanced filtering based on high-level science criteria derived from observatory ADP analyses (e.g., all ALMA data for a galaxy type with detected spectral lines) would be valuable, promoting findability in line with FAIR⁵ principles.
- **Movies:** most of the targets observed by radio observatories are not changing rapidly in time, such that data from multiple observations can be combined to form one single image. For a few targets, though, such as the Sun, planets (and their atmospheres), and active black holes, it will be critical to combine data only on short timescales, thus forming movies of images. It is important to note that standardized practices for astronomical movies are currently lacking. This gap presents an opportunity to establish uniform data formats and to advance the algorithms employed in their creation, such as those enabling temporal regularization in imaging.

4 Long-term Vision and Goals

The long-term vision for ADPs is to establish a sustainable and scalable framework that supports the diverse needs of the scientific community. This vision encompasses several key objectives:

- **“Don’t let the perfect be the enemy of the good-enough.”:** Observatories need to be less risk-averse, and consider rolling out new products (with proper documentation) even if they cannot be produced for all use cases.
- **Scalability:** Develop ADP-focused infrastructures (e.g. compute infrastructures) that can handle the increasing volume and complexity of observational data.
- **Sustainability:** Ensure the long-term viability of ADP initiatives through coordinated efforts and resource optimization. This can include ADP standards as well as ADP software pipelines.
- **Innovation:** Leverage emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and cloud computing, to enhance the capabilities of ADPs and/or their scientific utility.
- **Science-focused interoperability:** Make science products that are high-level (i.e. they do not require observatory-specific knowledge) and interoperable, across fields and wavelengths.
- **Community engagement:** Foster a collaborative ecosystem where researchers, developers, and observatories work together to advance ADP development.
- **ADP credit and recognition:** Establish mechanisms to properly credit ADP and ADP software developers, ensuring their contributions are recognized and helping to promote and retain this valuable expertise.

Realizing this vision requires a concerted effort to address the technical, organizational, and cultural challenges associated with ADP implementation. By prioritizing these objectives, the radio astronomy community can ensure that ADPs move at the forefront of scientific work.

⁴ALMACAL is a survey that utilizes calibration data from ALMA, originally obtained during routine observations, to conduct scientific analyses.

⁵FAIR data is data which meets the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

5 Observatory Initiatives

Several observatories have led the way in developing and implementing ADPs, offering valuable insights and lessons for the entire community. For instance,

- **Square Kilometre Array Observatory (SKAO):** Within the SKAO, processing of data to produce calibrated data products is considered to be a fundamental observatory function. This is required to address the otherwise impossible issues of transferring and storing the raw data and to ensure that data products meet quality assurance standards having been generated by known and trusted pipelines.

The SKAO framework categorizes data products into two key types:

- **Observatory Data Products (ODPs):** These calibrated products, generated by SKAO workflows, include image cubes, calibrated and averaged visibilities, pulsar timing solutions, sieved pulsar and transient candidate lists.
 - **ADPs:** In the SKA framework, ADPs are defined as user-generated products resulting from detailed modeling and cross-observation comparisons, typically developed within the SKA Regional Centre Network. While this definition is tailored to the specific operational model of the SKA, it aligns in spirit with the broader concept of ADPs considered in this paper.
- **VLA Sky Survey (VLASS):** VLASS is an initiative by the NRAO to map the entire sky visible to the VLA from 2-4 GHz using on-the-fly mapping and provide calibrated data and images (with Stokes products) to the community. Image products include “Quick Look” continuum images produced at a short turnaround time so that they can be used quickly as reference images for science such as transient identification. Other image products include higher fidelity “Single Epoch” images made with iterative auto-masking and self-calibration. The Observatory will also produce “coarse cubes” across frequency space with Stokes IUV planes, and final “cumulative images”.
 - **NRAO Science Ready Data Products initiative:** The NRAO SRDP initiative encompasses both ALMA and VLA data. For the VLA, raw data are run through a CASA calibration and imaging pipeline and the calibration and images undergo quality assessment (QA) and—upon QA acceptance—calibration products and images are ingested into the NRAO data archive. Then for ALMA, users can create customized data cubes requesting spectral averaging and/or higher or lower angular resolution. Then the existing calibration is restored and a custom image pipeline recipe is executed on the data and run using the latest release of the pipeline. Upon QA acceptance, these images are ingested into the NRAO archive. For both observatories, calibrated visibility data can be requested on-demand for the generation of ADPs by users. The calibrated data are automatically generated if an archived pipeline calibration is available. Images from VLA, ALMA, and VLASS can be viewed from within the archives via a CARTA⁶ server.
 - **ALMA:** ALMA Large Programs are generating a wealth of ADPs, and the ALMA Regional Centers (ARCs) are now providing advanced products, such as calibrated visibilities, further supporting the community’s data needs. These efforts align with the ALMA2030 vision, which underscores the critical role of archival products in achieving the observatory’s scientific goals. This vision highlights the need for robust archives that not only store observational data but also provide tools for efficient data retrieval and analysis, ensuring long-term accessibility and maximizing scientific impact.
 - **EASC ADP Initiative:** The EASC (ESO ALMA Support Center) ADP Initiative has emphasized the importance of community engagement, process standardization, and the development of scalable processing pipelines to support ADP generation and management. A key aspect of its long-term strategy is building community-driven, interoperable solutions while ensuring robust

⁶Cube Analysis and Rendering Tool for Astronomy

quality assurance frameworks and integrating advanced computational tools. Additionally, the initiative fosters collaboration among observatories to maintain consistency and reliability in data products. By aligning its efforts with the evolving needs of the astronomical community and leveraging technological advancements, the initiative aims to establish ADPs as essential tools for scientific discovery.

- **LOFAR:** As part of the ongoing upgrade to LOFAR2.0, LOFAR ERIC⁷ has recognized the importance of ADPs in enhancing both the accessibility and scientific impact of the telescope. To support this, LOFAR2.0 Data Services are being developed to provide a range of standardized ADPs through a FAIR data archive, initially focusing on imaging and pulsar timing, with plans to expand over time. Currently, LOFAR is at the ADP discovery stage, drawing inspiration from collaborations with other observatories to shape its strategy for service development and scientific exploitation. A key aspect of this effort has been the active engagement of the community in the generation of ADPs, which has proven pivotal. Moving forward, LOFAR plans to transition towards a more centralized approach, while recognizing that building trust within the community is essential. To facilitate this, LOFAR is leveraging ‘community ambassadors’ and involving the scientific community in data acceptance processes, such as quality control. Additionally, the observatory is working to define standards for integrating community-developed codes and workflows into its operations. A crucial lesson learned from these efforts is the need for early policy definition to ensure a smooth transition and effective collaboration.
- **Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI):** ADPs, albeit a recent concept for radio observatories, have been common for decades for optical observatories. Among those, the STScI holds a special place for their experience with developing an infrastructure for High-Level Science Products and ingesting community-made ADPs (e.g., from legacy and large programs) through MAST that broadens the use of observatory data. The STScI has demonstrated the potential of ADPs to increase user engagement and facilitate discoveries, particularly in under-represented communities. Their emphasis on equity and inclusiveness serves as a model for other observatories.
- The **ESO Science Archive** hosts the data from the optical/infrared instruments operated by ESO within the La Silla-Paranal Observatory and is open to access worldwide without restrictions. Raw data have been systematically collected there for the whole suite of instruments since the beginning of VLT operations in 1999, with earlier data from La Silla often also available. Processed data started to be published in the archive in 2011, with the first wave of data releases from the first generation of ESO Public Surveys. The scope of such releases gradually increased beyond Public Surveys and now, the archive counts 90+ collections of processed data. They are a mix of contributions from the community, usually focused on specific science cases, and sweeping processing by instrument (mode) carried out at ESO with the data processing pipelines that are also made available for community use. This scheme of filling the archive with processed data, which is called Phase 3 since it follows and extends the submission and selection of observing proposals (Phase 1) and the definition and execution of observations (Phase 2), will continue into the ELT⁸ era. As a measure of user adoption, the download of processed data now exceeds that of their raw counterpart. Let us finally note that the systematic science processing at ESO required to feed the corresponding data collections has triggered a virtuous cycle of progressive improvement of the processing tools (aka pipelines).

These initiatives underscore the need for observatories to adopt a proactive approach to ADP development, leveraging their unique capabilities and resources to address the evolving needs of the scientific community.

⁷European Research Infrastructure Consortium

⁸Extremely Large Telescope

6 Engaging the Community

Community engagement is critical for the success of ADP initiatives. Strategies to enhance engagement include:

- **Capacity building:** Provide training and resources to enable researchers to effectively use and contribute to ADPs.
- **Collaborative platforms:** Develop interoperable platforms that facilitate collaboration among researchers, developers, and observatories.
- **Quality assurance:** Implement formal (peer-)review processes to ensure the reliability of ADPs, either on the observatory or journal side. An example could be adopting a scheme like the “code review” for JOSS that can be submitted alongside/in tandem with AAS journals. The review here would focus on availability of code, reproducibility, documentation availability, archiving (data and software DOI).
- **Broad participation:** Promote initiatives that enhance the participation of research-disadvantaged groups in ADP development and use.

Case studies from other fields, such as genomics and Earth observation (ADD REFERENCE), highlight the transformative impact of community-driven approaches to data management and analysis. By adopting similar strategies, the radio astronomy community can maximize the scientific and societal benefits of ADPs.

7 Potential Issues

The increased usage of ADPs may pose new challenges.

- **Balancing transparency and accessibility:** While ADPs can be seen as a “black box”, potentially leading to a loss of expertise, they also enable a broader range of researchers to conduct science more effectively. There will always be experts who look under the hood, but ADPs empower those who wouldn’t otherwise engage at this level or with radio data as a whole.
- **Maximizing impact and usability:** The risk of developing ADPs that are either too constrained or not widely useful should be mitigated by aiming to maximize the product of impact \times usability, ensuring that ADPs serve the broader scientific community. This should be discussed continuously with the community.
- **Ensuring provenance and transparency:** Users must be able to trace how an ADP was derived from lower-level data, requiring clear provenance records, including software details, critical parameters, and standardized metadata.
- **Mitigating misuse without hindering progress:** While data misuse is a concern, it should not prevent development; instead, ensuring provenance clarity (e.g., through DOIs, references, and appropriate labeling such as “quicklook”) can help users interpret data correctly while still enabling progress.
- **Balancing maintenance burden and retaining expertise:** While maintaining ADPs within the observatory can be a resource burden, failing to do so risks losing expertise when originators leave the field, highlighting the need for sustainable integration of ADPs into observatory workflows.

8 Strategic Developments and Next Steps

The successful implementation of ADPs requires a global strategic approach that addresses both technical and organizational challenges. It is also something that needs to be shared/discussed among observatories and together with the community, as Science becomes more and more Open. Key areas of focus include:

- **ADPCG:** Establish an Advanced Data Products Coordination Group (ADPCG) to foster collaboration, standardization, and strategic alignment across radio observatories and teams developing and managing radio ADPs. This group encourages that data products are designed with interoperability, scalability, and scientific value in mind.
- **Prioritizing automation of routine tasks:** Observatories' priority in developing ADPs should initially focus on eliminating routine, scientifically uninteresting tasks for users (e.g., extracting point sources from images).
- **Frameworks, standards, and community integration:** Define schemas and standards to ensure ADPs from various sources are understandable and interoperable; implement crediting mechanisms (e.g., deep links, DOIs, credit statements) to incentivize contributions and ensure proper recognition; develop a structured process for observatories (and other ADP producers) to integrate mature community-developed techniques and tools; and implement a cost-benefit methodology that accounts for storage, computation, maintenance, and scientific value, recognizing and incorporating widely accepted community techniques.
- **Pipeline development and quality assurance:** Develop advanced data processing pipelines, with possible integration, if useful, of machine learning algorithms for automated quality assurance and data analysis; and establish comprehensive QA processes that ensure the accuracy, consistency, and reliability of ADPs.
- **Interoperable, user-friendly archives and tools:** Develop integrated archives that support seamless data integration across observatories and research platforms, enabling cross-archive searches, user-friendly web-based interfaces for data exploration, programmatic access for advanced analysis, and create intuitive user interfaces and tools that simplify access to and analysis of ADPs, catering to both novice and expert users.
- **Scalable, efficient, and cost-effective infrastructure:** Develop scalable computational and storage infrastructure to handle increasing data volumes and complexity, while implementing efficient and cost-effective practices for data processing, storage, and operations.
- **Collaboration platforms and interdisciplinary partnerships:** Develop platforms that encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing among researchers, developers, and observatories; and foster partnerships with other scientific disciplines to adopt, adapt, and leverage innovative technologies, methodologies, and best practices for ADP development and utilization.

By addressing these strategic priorities, the radio astronomy community can help ADPs become an essential element of scientific progress.

9 Conclusions

ADPs present a significant opportunity for radio observatories to boost scientific productivity, accessibility, and sustainability. By adopting a strategic and community-oriented approach to ADP development, observatories can effectively address the challenges posed by increasing data volumes and evolving scientific requirements, which will inevitably increase the need for centralized/high-performance computing resources. By providing the community with ADPs, observatories can mitigate the risks of “astro-cracizing” science, thus ensuring equitable access to high-quality, science-ready data.

The insights and recommendations presented in this paper serve as a solid foundation for realizing the full potential of ADPs, paving the way for a new era of groundbreaking discoveries in radio astronomy.